

CORRELATION BETWEEN DTPA-EXTRACTABLE MICRONUTRIENTS AND SOIL PROPERTIES IN THE SOILS OF WAGHODIA, VADODARA DISTRICT, GUJARAT

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MS Received: 07.03.2024; MS Revised:08.04.2025; MS Accepted:09.04.2025)

MS 3380

(RESEARCH PAPER IN SOIL SCIENCE AND AGRICULTURAL CHEMISTRY)

Abstract

Seventy-five soil samples from five pedons of the Instructional farm, College of Agriculture, Parul University, and Waghodiya of Vadodara were studied for the vertical distribution of DTPA extractable. Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn and their relationship with some soil properties. Soil pH, CaCO₃, organic carbon, and particle-size distribution strongly influenced the distribution of these micronutrients. The content of the micronutrient increased with an increase in organic carbon and decreased with an increase in pH and CaCO₃. There was a decreasing trend for the distribution of these micronutrients concerning depth.

The soils were very deep, moderate to strongly alkaline in reaction in nature (pH 6.80 to 8.40) with very low to high organic carbon content (0.01 to 0.80 %), low to high in calcium carbonate (07.03 to 13.3 %) respectively. The soil texture ranged from sandy loam to sandy clay loam in upland pedons while sandy clay loam to clay in pedons cultivated plains. In general, relatively low bulk density was recorded at surface horizons compared to sub-surface layers. Maximum water holding capacity, pore space, and volume expansion increased with soil depth. The DTPA extractable micronutrients of available Manganese and Copper were sufficient but Zinc and Iron were deficient in soils.

Keywords: Available micronutrients, alkaline soil, soil horizons.

Introduction

It is known that micronutrients are held within the mineral matter (Miller *et al.*, 1986) and finer fractions of soils (Sharma *et al.*, 2006). The availability of micronutrients is sensitive to changes in soil environment as well as physiographic; however, land use and landscape position may be the dominant factors of soil properties. Traditionally status of micronutrients was studied in only surface horizons (Takkar *et al.*, 1989). The sub-soil micronutrient status, which varies in the soil profile depending upon parent materials, landforms, climatic conditions, natural vegetation, and land use pattern (Deka *et al.*, 1996), is an important characteristic of knowing the soil resources, especially for crop nutrition practices. The micronutrients essential for plants are also indispensable for human beings, Zn and Fe are the most important nutrients and nearly half of the Indian soils are deficient in Zn and 15% in Fe. Available zinc in Gujarat soils ranges between 0.25 to 2.58 mg kg⁻¹. Nearly 24% soils of Gujarat state are Zn deficient and 58% soils of North Gujarat are found deficient to medium in available zinc status (Dangarwala *et al.*, 1983). These soils are commonly found in areas of Vertisols and associated soils covering 4.9 M ha in Gujarat (NBSS Staff 1988).

Micronutrients are important for maintaining soil health and also increasing the productivity of crops as they play vital roles in plant metabolism. These are needed in very small amounts. The deficiencies of micronutrients have become major constraints to the productivity, stability, and sustainability of soils. The availability of micronutrients is influenced by their distribution in soil and other physio-chemical properties of soil. Soils with finer particles and with higher organic matter can generally provide a great reserve of these elements whereas coarse-textured soils such as sand have fewer reserves and tend to get depleted rather quickly (Bhanwaria *et al.* 2011).

Materials and Methods

Study area Waghodia Taluka is located in the Vadodara district. Geographically the area lies between 73°17' to 73°33'E longitude and 22°12'to 22°21'N latitude. The total geographical area of the Taluka is 585.12km.

The mean annual temperature is 27.9°C with a mean summer temperature of 31.1°C and a mean winter temperature of 23.3°C. May is the hottest month with 39.5°C mean daily maximum temperature and January is the coldest month with 12.7°C mean daily minimum temperature. The mean annual rainfall of the area is around 869 mm, received mainly during the southwest monsoon from June to September. Major crops grown in this area are pigeon pea (*Cajanuscajan*), maize (*Zea mays*), cotton (*Gossypiumhirsutum*), sugarcane (*Saccharumofficinarum*), wheat

(*Triticumaestivum*) and green gram (*Vignaradiata*) with 90 to 120 days of length of growing period (LGP). The natural vegetation of the area comprised of *Azadirachtaindica*, *Prosopisjuliflora*, *Prosopis cineraria*, *Doob(Cynodondactylon)*, *Babool (Acacia arabica)*, *Peepal(Ficus religiosa)*.

The site and morphological characteristics of these soils were recorded and horizon-wise soil samples were collected (Soil Survey Division Staff 1995). The mechanical composition of soils was estimated by following the international pipette method (Piper 1966). For estimation of saturated hydraulic conductivity, 200 g of air-dry sample (2 mm) was dumped in one motion in the permeameter that was fitted with a screen and filter paper. The permeameter was then tapped 100 times to attain a uniform bulk density. After saturating the soil with distilled water, the saturated hydraulic conductivity was measured using the constant head method of Richards (1954). Calcium carbonate (Piper 1966), soil organic carbon (Walkley and Black 1934), pH, electrical conductivity Jackson (1973), Available Nitrogen was determined by Subbaiah and Asija (1956). Available phosphorus was estimated calorimetrically as per the method given by Jackson (1973).while Available potassium by Jackson (1973).Micronutrient content with physicochemical properties of the soils as suggested n (Lindsay and Norvell, 1978) and analyzed with the help of Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion**Soil site characteristics of Waghodiya of Vadodara**

The characteristics of the five soil pedons are presented in excavated the representative soil profile. The details about the location of the soil profile, name of soil series latitude and longitude, Mean Annual Rainfall (MAR), Mean Annual Temperature (MAT) (°C) and topography, etc. are given in Table 1.

The soils of Patiypura P1 and P2 are observed to be Plateau and uneven slope lands in topography to be slightly undulating, that of Tawara pedon P3, P4, and Limda P5 were Plateau. The slope and drainage were recorded to be 1-2 percent except for pedons P3 and P4, medium and Imperfect of all pedons. The Erosion is nil to all pedons of receptivity variation in morphological characteristics of five profiles indicating that the soil varies in depth and color considerably depending upon the topographic situation. The morphological characteristics showed considerable variation in the nature and degree of horizon development reported by Raina (2008).The morphology of the Vertisols indicated that the soils were deep to very deep (more than 90 cm) Abhishek Jangir(2018). The cracks were 2 to 10 cm wide at the surface and extended up to a depth of 50 cm. The pressure faces were observed in all

the profiles. Slicker sides were well developed and were tilted to an angle of 45-60 degrees from the horizontal. In pedons 1, 2, 3, and 4 the effervescence (with 10% HCl) was slight whereas in pedons 5, it was strong to violent which attributed the process of diffuse powdery from of CaCO₃. Calcium carbonate was observed throughout the depth of all soils. Malode and Patil (2014).

Available Zinc

DTPA-extractable zinc content in soils varied from 0.01 to 0.27 mg kg⁻¹. More than 80% of the surface soil samples could be rated as deficient in available zinc out of seventy-five soil samples from five pedons of Waghodiya of Vadodara Gujarat, below the critical limit of 0.6 mg kg⁻¹ (Katyal, 1985). Pedon 1 to 5 appeared to be deficient in zinc, while others of surface soils were above the critical level. All the pedons were available zinc showed decreasing trend with increasing soil depth. The lower content of zinc in black soils is due to its fixation by clay (Manohar, 1974) or due to high pH values which have resulted in the formation of insoluble compounds of zinc (Tandon, 1995). Available Zn content was significantly and negatively correlated ($r = -0.60^{**}$) with calcium carbonate. Sand and silt contents of soil also had a negative correlation but organic carbon and clay had a positive correlation with DTPA extractable Zn content of the soils.

Available Copper

The DTPA extractable copper in these soils ranged from 0.20 to 2.10 mg kg⁻¹ with a mean value of 0.67 mg kg⁻¹. Considering the critical limit of 0.2 mg kg⁻¹ for Cu for normal plant growth (Katyal and Randha, 1983), the soils are rated adequate in available Cu. Soil pH and CaCO₃ content had a negative correlation with copper but organic carbon ($r=0.50^{**}$) and clay ($r=0.39^{*}$) had a significantly positive relation with Cu content (Table 2). These findings collaborate with the results of Patil and Mukhopadhyay (2011); and Thakur *et al.* (2011).

Available Iron

These soils' DTPA extractable iron content varied between 0.97 to 23.89 mg kg⁻¹. Considering the critical limit of 4.5 mg kg⁻¹ for Fe (Lindsay and Norvell, 1978, Ramamurthy and Bajaj 1969), the soils are rated adequate in available Fe. Available Fe content was significantly and negatively correlated with calcium carbonate and soil reaction. These results agree with the findings of Patil *et al.* (2016), Satyavathi and Reddy (2004).

Available Manganese

The DTPA extractable manganese content of these soils varied from 2.90 to 53.36 mg kg⁻¹. Considering the critical limit of 3 mg kg⁻¹ for manganese as suggested by Takkar *et al.* (1989), pedons P5 are deficient in Mn. Available Mn content was significantly and positively correlated with calcium carbonate ($r = 0.32^{**}$) and clay ($r = 0.36^{**}$) content of the soil (Table 2).

In general, calcium carbonate increased the availability of micronutrients to the formation of their soluble hydroxides at higher pH (Sahoo *et al.*, 1995). Contrary to this, organic carbon had positive influence on DTPA-micronutrients due to complexation (Thampatti and Jose, 2006).

Conclusion

The DTPA extractable micronutrient distribution in soils of Waghodiya of Vadodara showed nutrient status of soils with profile P1 to P5. The surface soil pedons were Very low to low in available Zn, however, all the Pedon P1 to P5 showed low status. The available Zn content in soil profiles showed a decreasing trend with soil depth. All the soil horizons showed sufficiency in available copper. Available iron content was sufficient in surface and deficient in subsurface particularly in soils having CaCO₃. Available Mn was sufficient in all the soil profiles. Soil properties such as pH, and CaCO₃ showed negative

correlations and organic carbon and texture showed positive correlations with available micronutrients.

These observations point out those 75 and 85 % soil samples of Waghodia of the Vadodara district of Gujarat are deficient in DTPA-Zn and Fe respectively and need zinc fertilization for sustainable crop production. Higher amounts of these micronutrient cations were found in surface layers. The soil properties had a definite influence on their availability.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to DR. P. C. Patel, the Ex. Program coordinator, KVK Anand, Gujarat., and Dr. K. G. Patel, the Dean, and Principal, College of Agriculture, Parul University, Waghodia, Gujarat.

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Table 1 Soil- site Characteristics of Waghodia, of Vadodara District, Gujrat state.

Location	Latitude	Longitude	MAR (mm)	MAT (°C)	Topography	Drainage	Slope (%)	Erosion	Natural vegetation
Patiyapura	22° 16'.32.2 "	73° 25' 29".8	869	30 °C	Plateau and uneven slope land	well	1-2	Nil	Mango (Mangifera indica), Doob (Cynodondactylon), Babool (Acacia Arabica), Neem (Meliaradichata), Gumma (Leucasaspera), Peepal (Ficus religious)
Tawara	22° 16'.44.0 "	73° 25' 01".7	869	35 °C	Plateau	well	1-3	Nil	Mango (Mangifera indica), Gumma (Leucasaspera), Palm (Borassusflabellifer), Gorkhul (Tribulusterrestr)
Limda	22° 29'.24.6 "	73° 36' 34".5	750	36 °C	Plateau	M. well	1-2	Nil	Doob (cynodondactylon), Babool (Acacia Arabica),

(* MAR- Marginal annual rainfall, MAT- Marginal annual temperature)

Table 2. Physico-Chemical Properties and DTPA-Extractable Micronutrient Cations (mg kg⁻¹) in Soils of Waghodia, Vadodara District, Gujarat.

Location	Horizon	Depth (cm)	pH	EC (d Sm ⁻³)	Soil Texture			Available Micro Nutrient status (mg kg ⁻¹)				OC (%)	CaCO ₃ (%)
					Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Cu	Fe	Mn	Zn		
<i>Patiyapura-1 Fine, Semectitic, hyperthermic Vertic Haplustepts</i>													
Patiyapura P 1	AP	0-15	6.90	0.48	24.9	22.4	52.7	0.32	8.53	48.40	0.16	0.40	11.33
	A	15-27	7.52	0.46	23.1	20.8	56.1	0.30	7.22	41.20	0.09	0.34	10.01
	Bw	27-40	7.60	0.42	21.2	19.3	59.4	0.25	6.01	33.3	0.02	0.21	09.23
	Bssk	40-70	7.57	0.41	19.3	18.2	62.5	0.20	4.21	21.01	0.02	0.01	07.03
<i>Patiyapura-2 Fine, Semectitic, hyperthermic Vertic Haplustepts</i>													
Patiyapura P2	AP	0-15	7.30	0.44	23.9	22.1	53.9	0.44	23.89	48.40	0.16	0.40	11.97
	A	15-25	7.87	0.42	22.2	21.2	56.6	0.40	19.27	41.01	0.09	0.31	11.07
	Bw	25-65	7.88	0.41	19.1	19.3	61.6	0.24	17.22	32.2	0.01	0.21	09.73
<i>Tawara-1 Fine- loamy, mixed hyperthermic Typic Haplustepts</i>													
Tawra P3	AP	0-15	7.00	0.49	24.1	22.1	53.8	0.41	17.82	7.45	0.20	0.80	09.41
	A	15-30	7.48	0.55	22.8	20.2	56.8	0.33	14.81	5.02	0.19	0.62	09.21
	Bw	30-65	7.5	0.47	21.2	19.1	59.6	0.21	11.32	2.90	0.11	0.41	08.43
<i>Tawara-2 Fine- loamy, mixed hyperthermic Typic Haplustepts</i>													
Tawra P4	AP	0-15	6.80	0.44	21.9	20.8	57.3	0.39	15.44	53.36	0.27	0.50	09.92
	A	15-30	7.22	0.41	19.3	19.1	61.6	0.31	11.00	41.50	0.20	0.51	07.73
	Bw	30-77	7.63	0.40	18.6	17.5	63.9	0.20	06.02	30.30	0.17	0.32	07.10
<i>Limda-1 Very Fine Smectitic, hyperthermic Typic Haplustepts</i>													
Limda P5	AP	0-15	8.02	0.85	17.8	26.2	63.9	2.10	03.94	07.24	0.21	0.54	13.3
	A	15-30	8.21	0.60	16.3	21.9	61.8	1.72	02.63	06.10	0.13	0.30	11.2
	Bw	30-49	8.36	0.42	14.4	19.7	65.9	1.42	01.92	02.91	0.07	0.19	07.91
	Bssk	49-75	8.40	0.42	13.1	17.2	69.1	0.94	0.97	02.97	0.01	0.09	07.10

Table 3: Correlation between Soil Properties and Available Micronutrients in the Soils of Waghodia, Vadodara District, Gujarat

Soil characteristics	DTPA- Zn	DTPA- Cu	DTPA- Fe	DTPA- Mn
pH	-0.587	0.620	-0.546	-0.589
EC	0.396	0.736	-0.211	-0.395
OC	0.831	-0.007	0.489	-0.005
CaCO ₃	0.358	0.405	0.331	0.238